

ADVANCING FEMALE FERTILITY AND LIVESTOCK GENETICS THROUGH MOLECULAR MARKERS

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Abstract:

Genetic markers, which are genes or DNA sequences with known positions on chromosomes, are invaluable tools in modern animal breeding. These markers, detectable through various molecular techniques, provide precise genetic information, enabling better management of animal genetic resources. The advancements in molecular genetics have led to the development of numerous types of molecular markers, each with distinct strengths and weaknesses. Among the most significant markers are Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP), Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP) and Microsatellite markers, among others. These markers are widely utilized in genome mapping, gene tagging, genetic diversity assessment, phylogenetic analysis, and forensic investigations. Fertility, a critical aspect of animal production, particularly in dairy farms, can be significantly impacted by these genetic markers. Heritability estimates, which quantify the proportion of additive genetic variation, are crucial in selecting superior animals within breeds, thus improving reproductive efficiency. Female fertility, influenced by complex biological processes, is regulated by various molecular markers that control ovarian function, folliculogenesis, oogenesis, ovulation, puberty, the estrous cycle, pregnancy, prenatal mortality, parturition and the postpartum period. The careful selection and application of these markers in

well-designed studies can expedite the identification of genes involved in quantitative trait loci (QTL), enhancing marker-assisted selection and improving overall animal genetics. Molecular markers are essential for understanding and improving female fertility by regulating critical reproductive processes such as ovarian function, oogenesis and embryogenesis. Integrating these markers with reproductive biotechnologies can accelerate genetic improvements, enhancing reproductive traits and overall productivity in livestock. As research advances, the strategic use of molecular markers will play a crucial role in sustainable livestock breeding and genetic health.

Keywords: Genetic markers, Molecular genetics, Fertility, Ovarian function, Folliculogenesis, Marker-assisted selection, Quantitative trait loci (QTL), Animal breeding.

Introduction

A genetic marker is a gene or DNA sequence with a known position on a chromosome. It is a variation that can be detected and measured through appropriate methods, allowing the identification of a specific genotype. These chromosomal or DNA-level variations act as genetic markers. The significant advancements in molecular genetics have paved the way for genomics, leading to the development of new types of molecular markers for improving the genetics of farm animals. These markers offer more precise genetic information and a deeper understanding of animal genetic resources. However, scientists who are not well-versed in various molecular techniques may find them confusing, as each technique has its own strengths and weaknesses (Al-Samarai and Al-Kazaz, 2015).

Molecular markers are highly valued for their stability, cost-effectiveness, and ease of use, making them an extremely popular tool for various applications such as genome mapping, gene tagging, assessing genetic diversity, conducting phylogenetic analysis and performing forensic investigations. Over the past three decades, numerous molecular marker techniques have been developed and utilized globally in diverse systems (Grover and Sharma, 2016).

Maintaining high reproductive efficiency is crucial in modern animal production. Several reproductive traits in both females and males are significant. In females, ovulation rate, uterine capacity, and embryo survival are important traits, with embryo survival also being genetically influenced by the embryo itself. Recent focus has been on hormone concentrations in both sexes and the regulation of hormone receptors. Genetics play a fundamental role in controlling these reproductive traits. (Rothschild, 1996).

Heritability estimates, which range from 0 to 1, quantify the proportion of additive genetic variation that can be influenced by selecting superior animals within a breed or line. Fertility is critically important for dairy farms, as reproductive issues can result in significant direct and indirect costs. These costs include lost income from milk sales due to fewer calves produced annually, increased semen costs from a higher number of artificial inseminations per conception, expenses for treatments and veterinary services and additional costs from culling long-term infertile animals (Mahmoud and Nawito, 2012).

There are several genetic markers types related to fertility are:

1. Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP)
2. Single Strand Conformation Polymorphism (SSCP)
3. Randomly Amplified Polymorphic DNA (RAPD)
4. Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphism (AFLP) Markers,
5. Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP),
6. Simple Sequence Length Polymorphism (SSLP),
7. Variable Number Tandem Repeat (VNTR),
8. Short Tandem Repeat (STR),
9. Restriction Site Associated DNA (RAD)
10. Microsatellite Markers (Salisu *et al.*, 2018)

However, the wide range of molecular biology techniques available to produce molecular markers, along with their various biological implications, necessitates careful selection based on specific purposes. Well-designed studies utilizing these markers can significantly expedite the identification of genes involved in quantitative trait loci (QTL) for marker-assisted selection (Vignalet *et al.*, 2002).

- **Applications of Genetic Markers**

- I. Evaluation of the genetic diversity
- II. Sexing of pre-implantation embryos
- III. Identification of disease carrier
- IV. Gene mapping
- V. Markers assisted selection (MAS)
- VI. Detection of Quantitative trait Loci (QTL)

(Adamov *et al.*, 2012).

- **Molecular markers for female fertility**

Female fertility is a complex biological process influenced by numerous molecular markers. These markers play essential roles in regulating ovarian function, folliculogenesis, oogenesis, ovulation, puberty, the estrous cycle, pregnancy, prenatal mortality, parturition and the postpartum period.

List of molecular markers

Origin	Molecular markers
Regulation of Ovarian Function	1) FSHR 2) IGF-1 3) IGF-IR 4) CART
Follicogenesis, Oogenesis & Ovulation	1) GDF-9 2) BMP-15 3) Zar 1

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4) PER 1 5) QTL 6) uPA 7) Ptx 3 8) Survivin 9) FSHB
Puberty & Estrus Cycle	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) GPR54 2) SRC-3 3) STAR
Pregnancy & Prenatal Mortality	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) PRP-1 2) bPRP-1 3) CTSL 4) ITIH4 5) LIF 6) LIFR 7) EGFE 8) SERPINA14 / UTMP 9) OPN 10) Alu1 11) AREG 12) STAT 13) BTA 14) Ob gene
Parturition	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) FosB 2) Fos activate 3) PGE2 4) COX2
Post Partum Period	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) P450 2) CYP19 3) 335-pb

Regulation of Ovarian Function

- **Follicle-Stimulating Hormone Receptor (FSHR)**

FSHR is a G protein-coupled receptor that binds follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and plays a crucial role in ovarian follicle development and maturation. Variants in the FSHR gene have been associated with altered ovarian responses and are essential for the normal functioning of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis. FSHR is pivotal in the recruitment, growth, and maturation of ovarian follicles, making it vital for female fertility. Proper FSHR function ensures the development of high-quality oocytes capable of successful fertilization and embryonic development. Genetic and environmental factors influencing FSHR function can significantly

impact fertility, underscoring the importance of this receptor in reproductive health (De Pascali *et al.*, 2018).

Fig. 1. Representing Follicle stimulating hormone: α FSH (green), β FSH (orange) with receptor (FSHR, blue) (Bhartiya and Patel, 2021)

- **Role of FSHR in Animal Fertility: Ovarian Follicle Development**

The Follicle-Stimulating Hormone Receptor (FSHR) is essential for the recruitment and growth of ovarian follicles, which are crucial for successful reproduction. Proper FSHR function ensures the maturation of these follicles, leading to the release of viable oocytes. Insufficient FSHR function can result in anovulation or poor oocyte quality, significantly impacting fertility (Park *et al.*, 2022).

- **Mechanisms of FSHR in Ovarian Follicle Development**
- **Follicle Recruitment and Growth:**

FSHR is expressed on the granulosa cells of ovarian follicles. The binding of FSH to FSHR stimulates granulosa cell proliferation and follicular growth, a process known as folliculogenesis. During the early stages of follicle development, FSHR mediates the transition from primordial follicles to primary follicles and subsequently to secondary and antral follicles. This progression is crucial for the selection of a dominant follicle that will ultimately ovulate (Recchia *et al.*, 2021)

- **Steroidogenesis:**

Activation of the follicle-stimulating hormone receptor (FSHR) boosts the production of steroid hormones, especially estradiol, by promoting the aromatase enzyme in granulosa cells. Estradiol is crucial for granulosa cell proliferation and the upkeep of follicular growth. Sufficient estradiol levels are essential for the positive feedback mechanism that triggers the pre-ovulatory luteinizing hormone (LH) surge, leading to ovulation (Das and Kumar, 2018).

Fig. 2. FSH and FSHR role in folliculogenesis, oogenesis and spermatogenesis (Recchia *et al.*, 2021).

4. Oocyte Maturation:

FSHR signaling is important for the resumption of reduction division (meiosis) in oocytes, that was arrested at the diplotene phase of prophase I stage until the pre-ovulatory surge. FSH-induced maturation of the oocyte is crucial for its competence to be fertilized. Proper FSHR function ensures the acquisition of developmental competence by the oocyte, which is essential for successful fertilization followed by embryonic development (Das and Kumar, 2018).

- **Consequences of FSHR dysfunction**
- **Anovulation:**

Anovulation, the failure to ovulate, can result from insufficient FSHR signaling. This insufficiency prevents ovarian follicles from reaching the antral stage, thus hindering the release of a mature oocyte. Genetic mutations or polymorphisms in the FSHR gene can impair receptor function, leading to conditions like primary ovarian insufficiency (POI) and other forms of infertility marked by anovulation. (Sharifiyazdi *et al.*, 2018).

- **Mutations:**

Both activating and inactivating mutations have been described in both the sexes and cause alteration of reproductive function, even though the phenotype is often more severe for female fertility. Activating mutations confer to FSHR a higher responsiveness to FSH, making it constitutively active even in the absence of the ligand. Inactivating mutations reduce the receptor function up to a total block, altering either the formation of the receptor-ligand complex or FSH signal transduction. FSHR inactivating mutations cause primary or secondary amenorrhea, infertility and premature ovarian failure (POF), whereas activating mutations can predispose to ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome (OHSS) (Bhartiya and Patel, 2021).

- **Polymorphisms:**

Approximately 1800 SNPs of the FSHR gene have been documented in the SNP database (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>). These SNPs are found either in the coding regions (exons, 8 SNPs) or within intronic regions of exons. Only one SNP is located in the 5' untranslated region of the FSHR mRNA at position -29 (ss2189241). Of the eight SNPs within coding regions, seven are situated in exon 10 at codon positions 307, 329, 449, 524, 567, 665, and 680. Six of these result in amino acid substitutions and are thus non-synonymous.

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of FSHR gene and protein(Bhartiya and Patel, 2021).

The two best-characterized polymorphisms in terms of allele frequencies and ethnic distribution are Ala307Thr (rs6165) and Ser680Asn (rs6166). These SNPs affect FSHR protein responsiveness to exogenous FSH, impacting the effectiveness of in vitro fertilization (IVF) treatment and the risk of developing severe ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome (OHSS) due to superovulation. SNPs at positions 307 and 680 of exon 10 are the most common in FSHR (Fig. 3) (Simoni *et al.*, 1997). Banerjee *et al.* (2021) have documented various pathologies resulting from FSHR dysfunction in both men and women, noting that these dysfunctions are more severe in women, leading to infertility, while in men, they typically result in subfertility.

- **FSHR isoforms:**

FSH exhibits pleiotropy, playing a role in diverse functions such as cellular growth, differentiation and steroidogenesis, which lead to the formation of a single large follicle or the daily production of millions of sperm. In mammals, a vast array of functional proteins is encoded by only 23,000 to 25,000 genes, likely through mechanisms like split genes and alternative mRNA splicing. This process allows multiple proteins to be generated from a single gene, with nearly half of the genes undergoing alternate splicing (Sharp, 1994). Four different FSHR isomers exist (Fig. 4) due to different splicing mechanisms of FSHR exons (Sairam and Babu, 2007 and Simoni *et al.*, 2002).

Fig. 4. Four alternately spliced FSHR isoforms as described earlier (Sairam and Babu, 2007).

Thus, the pre-mRNA of a single large gene coding for FSHR undergoes alternate splicing creating 4 different isoforms with similar N-terminus and different c-terminus. They have been reported in mice, rats, sheep, bovine species and as well as in humans. Human ovarian granulosa cells show the presence of all 4 transcripts.

- **Poor Oocyte Quality:**

Inadequate FSHR function can result in the development of follicles with poor oocyte quality. These oocytes may display chromosomal abnormalities, poor cytoplasmic maturation, and reduced developmental competence. Poor oocyte quality directly affects fertilization rates, embryo quality, and pregnancy outcomes in both natural and assisted reproduction (Bhartiya and Patel, 2021).

- **Endocrine Disruptors:**

Environmental factors, such as exposure to endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs), can interfere with FSHR function. EDCs can mimic or block hormonal signaling, disrupting normal follicular development and function. Examples of EDCs include bisphenol A (BPA), phthalates, and certain pesticides, which have been shown to adversely affect ovarian function and fertility in various animal models (Zama *et al.*, 2016).

- **Insulin-Like Growth Factor 1 (IGF-1)**

Insulin-Like Growth Factor 1 (IGF-1) is a peptide hormone that plays vital roles in growth and development, including significant functions in the reproductive system. In the context of female animal fertility, IGF-1 regulates ovarian follicular growth and development. It enhances the sensitivity of ovarian follicles to Follicle-Stimulating Hormone (FSH), thereby promoting follicular maturation and steroidogenesis (Piau *et al.*, 2023).

- Mechanisms of IGF-1 in Ovarian Follicular Growth and Development
- Enhancement of FSH Sensitivity:

IGF-1 works synergistically with FSH to promote the growth and development of ovarian follicles. It enhances the responsiveness of granulosa cells to FSH by increasing the expression of FSH receptors (FSHR) on these cells. This heightened sensitivity allows for more efficient FSH signaling, which is essential for the progression of follicles from the early stages of development to the pre-ovulatory stage. (Zhou *et al.*, 2013).

Fig. 5. This scheme shows the influence of IGF1 on the maturation and aging process of oocytes. In vivo, the maturation of oocytes is stimulated by the pre-ovulatory surge of the luteinizing hormone (LH). The LH binds to LH receptors on mural granulosa cells and generates the production of specific epidermal growth factor-like peptides that transmit signals to the cumulus cells and the oocyte itself. The gonadotropins are commonly combined with epidermal growth factor (EGF) or EGF-like factors that are produced by follicular cells. It has been convincingly demonstrated that insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF1) enables the maturation of oocytes and aging through a phosphoinositide-3-kinase/v-akt murine thymoma viral oncogene homolog (PI3K/AKT)-dependent mechanism. Abbreviations: AMPK: activated protein kinase; GJ: gap-junctions; IGFR: insulin-like growth factor receptor; IRS: insulin receptor substrate; MIH: maturation-inducing hormone; MIH-R: maturation-inducing hormone receptor; mTOR: mammalian target of rapamycin, PTEN: Phosphatase and Tension Homolog; ROS: reactive oxygen species; S6K: S6 kinase; green plus: positive/activating effect; red arrows: negative effect (Kordowitzkiet *al.*, 2022).

4.2.1.1. Promotion of Follicular Maturation:

IGF-1 contributes to the proliferation and differentiation of granulosa cells within the follicles. This proliferation is crucial for follicle growth and the formation of the antral cavity. Granulosa cells nurture the developing oocyte and produce hormones necessary for follicular growth and oocyte maturation (Pisseletet *al.*, 1997).

- **Steroidogenesis:**

IGF-1 stimulates the production of steroid hormones, particularly by estrogen, through enhancing the activity of key enzymes involved in steroidogenesis, like aromatase. Estrogen produced by granulosa cells is crucial for the growth and maturation of the dominant follicle and also for the regulation of the estrous cycle (Bleach *et al.*, 2021).

- **Anti-Apoptotic Effects:**

IGF-1 exerts anti-apoptotic effects on ovarian follicles, decreasing the rate of follicular atresia (follicular regression) and thereby increasing the number of viable follicles available for ovulation. By preventing apoptosis in granulosa cells, IGF-1 promotes the survival and development of healthy follicles, which is critical for maintaining fertility. The expression of IGF1R in ovarian granulosa cells is crucial for steroidogenesis, follicle survival, and fertility in female mice (Jin *et al.*, 2011).

- **Consequences of IGF-1 Dysregulation**

- **Reduced Follicular Development:**

Insufficient levels of IGF-1 can lead to impaired follicular development. Follicles may fail to mature properly, resulting in reduced ovulation rates and lower fertility. Inadequate IGF-1

signaling can also lead to poor oocyte quality, affecting the chances of successful fertilization and embryo development (Jin *et al.*, 2011).

❖ **Altered Steroidogenesis:**

Dysregulation of IGF-1 can impact steroid hormone production, leading to hormonal imbalances that affect the reproductive cycle and ovarian function. Conditions such as polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) in animals have been associated with disruptions in IGF-1 signaling, leading to abnormal follicular development and ovulatory dysfunction.

❖ **Increased Follicular Atresia:**

Without the protective anti-apoptotic effects of IGF-1, there may be an increase in follicular atresia, reducing the number of viable follicles available for ovulation. This reduction in the follicular pool can lead to subfertility or infertility, especially in species with lower natural fecundity.

❖ **Genetic and Environmental Influences**

• **Genetic Factors:**

Genetic variations in the IGF-1 gene or its receptor (IGF-1R) can influence the expression and activity of IGF-1, affecting follicular development and fertility. Selective breeding programs in livestock aim to enhance fertility traits by selecting animals with favorable IGF-1 profiles.

• **Nutritional and Environmental Factors:**

Nutrition plays a vital role in IGF-1 production. Sufficient protein intake and overall nutritional status influence IGF-1 levels and consequently reproductive performance. Environmental stressors, such as heat stress or exposure to toxins, can disrupt IGF-1 signaling pathways, adversely affecting fertility.

❖ **Applications in Animal Reproduction Technologies**

• **Follicular Stimulation Protocols:**

IGF-1 administration can be used in follicular stimulation protocols to enhance ovarian response to FSH in assisted reproductive technologies (ART), such as superovulation and in vitro fertilization (IVF). By improving follicular development and oocyte quality, IGF-1 can increase the success rates of these reproductive technologies (Celestino *et al.*, 2018).

❖ **Cocaine- and Amphetamine-Regulated Transcript (CART)**

CART is a neuropeptide that influences energy balance and reproductive function. It has been found to inhibit the secretion of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), thus affecting ovarian function and fertility. Cocaine- and amphetamine-regulated transcript (CART) is a hypothalamic neuropeptide involved in both metabolic and reproductive regulation, suggesting that CART may play a role in reproductive inhibition during negative metabolic conditions. CART fibers are closely associated with 60% of GnRH cells, with the majority (80%) of these fibers originating from the arcuate nucleus (ARH) CART/pro-opiomelanocortin population. Electrophysiological

recordings in GnRH-green fluorescent protein rats showed that CART depolarizes GnRH cells post-synaptically. Additionally, CART fibers from the ARH are in close contact with Kiss1 cells in the ARH and anteroventral periventricular nucleus (AVPV). Recordings in Kiss1-GFP mice indicated that CART also depolarizes ARH Kiss1 cells post-synaptically, suggesting that CART may stimulate GnRH neurons both directly and indirectly through Kiss1 populations (True *et al.*, 2013).

CART protein and mRNA levels were examined by True *et al.* (2013) in two models of negative energy balance: caloric restriction (CR) and lactation. During CR, both CART mRNA levels and the number of CART-immunoreactive cells were suppressed in the ARH, but this suppression was not observed during lactation. In the AVPV, CART mRNA levels were also suppressed during CR, whereas lactation caused a significant increase in CART-immunoreactive cells. These findings suggest that CART is regulated differently in these two models of negative energy balance. In conclusion, both morphological and electrophysiological evidence identifies CART as a novel and potent stimulator of Kiss1 and GnRH neurons. The suppression of CART expression during negative metabolic conditions could contribute to the inhibition of the reproductive axis. (True *et al.*, 2013).

❖ Folliculogenesis, Oogenesis and Ovulation

- Growth Differentiation Factor 9 (GDF-9)

GDF-9 is a member of the transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β) superfamily and is critical for ovarian folliculogenesis. It regulates granulosa cell proliferation and differentiation, playing a pivotal role in oocyte maturation (Knight and Glister, 2006). Growth factors play an important role during early ovarian development and folliculogenesis, since they regulate the migration of germ cells to the gonadal ridge. They also act on follicle recruitment, proliferation/atresia of granulosa cells and theca, steroidogenesis, oocyte maturation, ovulation and luteinization. Among the growth factors, the growth differentiation factor 9 (GDF9) and the bone morphogenetic protein 15 (BMP15), belong to the transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β) (de Castro *et al.*, 2016).

Fig. 6. Role of growth differentiation factor 9 and bone morphogenetic protein 15 in ovarian function (de Castro *et al.*, 2016).

GDF9 and BMP15 are crucial in the transition of primordial follicles to primary follicles and play a significant role in the later stages of follicular development and maturation. They increase the expression of the steroidogenic acute regulatory protein, plasminogen activator, and luteinizing hormone receptor (LHR). These factors are also involved in the interactions between the oocyte and surrounding cumulus cells, regulating the absorption of amino acids, glycolysis, and cholesterol biosynthesis in cumulus cells. Although the exact mechanisms are not fully understood, *in vitro* studies suggest that GDF9 and BMP15 stimulate the growth of ovarian follicles and the proliferation of cumulus cells by inducing mitosis in granulosa and theca cells and the expression of genes associated with follicular maturation. Thus, seeking greater understanding of the action of these growth factors on the development of oocytes, the role of GDF9 and BMP15 in ovarian function (Castro *et al.*, 2016).

- **Bone Morphogenetic Protein 15 (BMP-15)**

BMP-15, a member of the TGF- β family, plays a critical role in regulating follicular development and oocyte maturation. Mutations in the BMP-15 gene can lead to fertility issues, such as ovarian dysgenesis. Bone morphogenetic protein 15 (BMP-15) is essential for the early phases of follicle development. Oocytes, through BMP-15, regulate the differentiation and activity of granulosa cells (GCs) and influence gene expression patterns in follicular somatic cells. BMP-15 is crucial for differentiating GCs and controlling their essential functions.

Oocyte-derived growth and differentiation factors like BMP-15 may simulate the oocyte's actions on GCs and cumulus cells (CCs) to enhance oocyte developmental competence *in vitro*. An *in vitro* 3D ovarian follicle culture supplemented with BMP-15 was examined to understand its role in the growth of ovarian follicles *in vitro*. While BMP-15 supplementation in 3D ovarian follicle culture aims to improve the effectiveness of *in vitro* follicle culture, there remains inconsistency in the developmental competence of mature oocytes (Jitjumnong and Tang, 2023).

- ❖ **Zygote Arrest 1 (Zar1)**

Zar1 is critical for early embryonic development, playing a key role in regulating maternal mRNA translation, which is essential for zygote formation and early embryogenesis (Rong *et al.*, 2019). Zygote arrest 1 (Zar1) is an ovary-specific maternal factor crucial during the oocyte-to-embryo transition in mice. Its expression is strictly confined to the oocyte, the zygote and, to a lesser extent, the 2-cell embryo. Tiziana *et al.* (2004) conducted Reverse Transcription (RT)-Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) analysis on a range of bovine tissues, oocytes, and pre-implantation *in vitro* produced embryos. Their results demonstrated the presence of a Zar1 ortholog in cattle. In adults, the gene is expressed in the ovary, testis, muscle, and myocardium. Additionally, the gene is expressed in the oocyte, the zygote, and throughout all stages of embryonic development up to the blastocyst formation. A semi-quantitative RT-PCR analysis showed that Zar1 levels remain steady throughout *in vitro* development, except at the 4-cell stage, where there is a notable increase. This rise in Zar1 expression was suppressed when fertilized oocytes were exposed to the RNA polymerase II inhibitor alpha-amanitin, suggesting that the transcription of Zar1 occurs specifically at the 4-cell stage (Breviniet *et al.*, 2004).

Zar1 is conserved in cattle but exhibits a different expression pattern compared to mice. In adult cattle, Zar1 expression is not restricted to the ovary; it is also found in the testis, muscle, and myocardium. In embryos, Zar1 expression extends beyond the oocyte-to-embryo transition. Notably, the detection of Zar1 transcription at the 4-cell stage marks the first characterization of a gene expressed in cattle embryos prior to the major onset of embryonic transcription (Memili and First, 2000).

❖ Survivin

Survivin is an inhibitor of apoptosis protein (IAP) that helps maintain granulosa cell viability, thereby supporting follicular development and oocyte survival, which are essential for overall fertility (Johnson, 2003). Caspases, a family of cysteine proteases, play crucial roles in mediating apoptosis and are categorized into two subgroups: initiator and effector. Initiator caspases, such as caspase-6, -8, and -9, contain domains that target specific apoptotic triggers, while effector caspases, including caspase-3 and -7, are activated by upstream initiator caspases. The activation of caspase-3 is the final step in the apoptotic cascade, leading to the cleavage of cellular substrates essential for cell survival. Caspase activity is indirectly regulated by the balance between anti-apoptotic and pro-apoptotic genes. Inhibitor of apoptosis proteins (IAPs) are characterized by the presence of up to three baculoviral IAP repeat (BIR) domains that bind caspases to directly suppress their activity. Among IAPs, survivin is a 16.5-kDa protein containing a single BIR domain and an extended carboxyl-terminal α -helix (Cohen, 1997; Cryns and Yuan, 1999; Salveson and Dixit, 1997; Deveraux *et al.*, 1997; Ambrosini *et al.*, 1997).

In fetal tissues of mice, survivin is abundantly expressed after embryonic day 11.5, but it is rarely present in most terminally differentiated adult tissues. However, survivin becomes prominently re-expressed in transformed cell lines and many tumors, suggesting that survivin may play a significant role in various immature or undifferentiated tissues. Survivin also known as a dual-functional protein which suppresses apoptosis and regulates cell division. It acts as an inhibitor of apoptosis by directly binding caspases, although the specific caspases that survivin binds to remain a topic of debate. Survivin has been shown to directly inhibit caspase-3 activity, although conflicting data have been reported previously (Kawamura *et al.*, 2003).

Structural analysis using X-ray crystallography suggests that survivin is unlikely to bind caspase-3 through its BIR domain. Instead, when survivin is phosphorylated at Thr34, it forms a complex with caspase-9 at the mitotic apparatus. Loss of this phosphorylation leads to the dissociation of the complex and triggers caspase-9-dependent apoptosis (Kondapuram *et al.*, 2023).

Centromere protein (INCENP) and Aurora kinase, both of which are chromosomal passenger proteins. Aurora-B kinase and INCENP are crucial for coordinating chromosome segregation during cell division. In yeasts and *Caenorhabditis elegans*, survivin homologs Bir1 and BIR-1 have been shown to physically and functionally interact with these proteins during cell division (Adams et al., 2001).

During cell division, disruption of survivin results in abnormal mitotic progression, marked by the presence of extra centrosomes, the formation of multipolar mitotic spindles, cytokinesis failure, and the production of multinucleated cells. Throughout mouse embryo development, various caspases, along with anti-apoptotic and pro-apoptotic genes, are expressed. (Cohen, 1997; Cryns and Yuan, 1999 and Salveson and Dixit, 1997). Among antiapoptotic genes, Bcl-2 was shown to express in the preimplantation embryos, but Bcl-2 null embryos are able to develop normally throughout the first half-period of gestation. In the IAP family of genes, mice with deletion of X-linked IAP (XIAP) and neuronal apoptosis inhibitory protein 1 (NAIP1) develop normally till adults. However, mouse embryos which lacks survivin showed embryonic lethality, but the occurrence of apoptosis in these embryos was not examined (Uren et al., 2000).

❖ **Puberty and Estrus Cycle**

• **G Protein-Coupled Receptor 54 (GPR54)**

GPR54, also known as Kiss1R, is crucial for initiating puberty by mediating the effects of kisspeptin on GnRH secretion, thus regulating the onset of reproductive capability. Puberty marks the culmination of a complex series of developmental events driven by the interplay between genetic factors and environmental cues, ultimately leading to reproductive maturity (Navarro et al., 2007).

Kisspeptins, derived from the KISS1 gene, were initially identified as metastasis suppressor peptides capable of binding to G protein-coupled receptors (GPR54) (Navenot *et al.*, 2009). They are highly potent in stimulating gonadotropin secretion, mainly through the induction of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) release. KISS1 also acts as a crucial integrator of peripheral inputs, such as gonadal steroids and nutritional signals, to regulate GnRH and gonadotropin secretion. The primary site of action for kisspeptins on the reproductive axis is the hypothalamus, where they activate GnRH release (Yeo and Colledge, 2018). In the rat hypothalamus, over 75% of GnRH neurons co-express GPR54 mRNA, and central administration of kisspeptin induces c-fos expression, an early marker of activation, in more than 85% of GnRH neurons. Additionally, kisspeptin has been shown to stimulate GnRH secretion in rat hypothalamic explants *ex vivo* and to induce GnRH release *in vivo* in sheep (Messenger, 2005).

Taken together, these data, strongly suggested that kisspeptins directly activate hypothalamic GnRH neurons, causing stimulation of GnRH secretion, which in turn elicits LH and FSH release from the pituitary (Messenger, 2005 and Castellano *et al.*, 2005).

Fig. 8. Shows the process involved in puberty initiation. As GnRH neurons are the final central pathway controlling the onset of puberty, Kisspeptin potently activates GnRH release via G protein-coupled receptor 54 (GPR54) (Xavier and William, 2010). The GnRH acts on the anterior pituitary to stimulate the release of the gonadotrophic hormones, (luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle stimulating hormone (FSH)). The gonadotrophic hormones act on the gonads (ovary and testes) to stimulate to produce sex steroids (testosterone in males and estrogen and progesterone in females), required for sexual maturation and gametogenesis (spermatogenesis in males and oogenesis in females) which is the maturation of accessory sex organs and to provide hormonal feedback loops that regulate GnRH and gonadotrophic hormone (FSH and LH) release under different physiological conditions (Olaniyan *et al.*, 2013).

Steroid Receptor Coactivator-3 (SRC-3)

SRC-3 is a transcriptional coactivator involved in steroid hormone receptor signalling. It regulates the expression of genes necessary for puberty and the estrous cycle. Steroid receptor coactivator-3 (SRC-3) is a coactivator of nuclear receptors in the SRC family, as demonstrated through in vitro assays. In mice, SRC-3 is expressed in a tissue-specific manner, predominantly found in oocytes, mammary glands, the hippocampus, olfactory bulb, smooth muscle, hepatocytes and vaginal epithelium. Genetic disruption of SRC-3 in mice results in a pleiotropic phenotype showing dwarfism, delayed puberty, reduced female reproductive function and blunted mammary gland development (Xu *et al.*, 2000).

Hormonal analysis suggests that SRC-3 is involved in the regulation of the growth hormone pathway and estrogen production, which may account for the observed phenotypes. Nuclear receptors rely on coactivators to facilitate the transcriptional activation of their target genes. The steroid receptor coactivator (SRC) family includes three recently identified coactivators: SRC-1, GRIP1 (also known as TIF2/SRC-2) and p/CIP (also known as RAC3/ACTR/AIB1/TRAM1/SRC-3). In vitro studies indicate that SRCs mediate transcriptional activation through multiple mechanisms, including...

- (i) Direct interaction with ligand-bound nuclear receptors
- (ii) Direct contact with certain general transcription factors such as TFIIB and TBP
- (iii) Interaction with common transcriptional coactivators such as CBP, p300 and p / CAF
- (iv) Interaction with other coactivators such as coactivator-associated arginine methyltransferase 1 (CARM-1), cancer-amplified transcriptional coactivator ASC-2, PPARG coactivator-1 (PGC-1) and steroid receptor RNA co-activator (SRA)
- (v) Participation in chromatin remodeling through their intrinsic histone acetyltransferase activity
- (vi) Enzymatic modification of other constituents of the coactivator complex

(McKenna *et al.*, 1999 and Chen *et al.*, 1999)

❖ Steroidogenic Acute Regulatory Protein (STAR)

STAR facilitates the transport of cholesterol into mitochondria, which is essential for steroid hormone biosynthesis and the production of sex steroids during the estrous cycle (Bassi *et al.*, 2021). The basic framework of steroidogenesis is consistent across steroidogenic cells, particularly in the initial mitochondrial steps. For example, the START domain-containing protein mediates cholesterol transport to the mitochondria, where it is converted to pregnenolone by the enzyme P450_{scc}. This process is conserved across steroidogenic cells (Strauss III and FitzGerald, 2019). The enzyme P450_{scc}, located on the inner mitochondrial membrane, highlights the critical role of mitochondria in steroidogenesis. While mitochondria share this common function, their structure, number, and dynamics vary significantly among different steroidogenic cell types, indicating they have roles beyond pregnenolone biosynthesis. The initial step in steroid hormone biosynthesis involves the enzymatic cleavage of a six-carbon side chain from the cholesterol molecule by the

20–22 desmolase/lyase activity of the cytochrome P450 side chain cleavage (P450_{scc}) enzyme system within the inner mitochondrial membrane (IMM)(Rone *et al.*, 2009 and Lin *et al.*, 2016). Steroidogenesis is a precisely compartmentalized, multistep enzymatic process within steroidogenic cells, involving various cellular compartments such as the cytoplasm, mitochondria and smooth endoplasmic reticulum (SER). The initiation of steroidogenesis, which includes the enzymatic cleavage of the cholesterol side chain, is consistent across steroidogenic cells. The enzyme P450_{scc}, located on the matrix side of the inner mitochondrial membrane (IMM), underscores the central role of mitochondria in this process. As a result, steroidogenic cells—such as adrenocortical cells in the adrenal glands, granulosa and theca cells in the ovary, Leydig cells in the testis and syncytial trophoblast cells in the placenta—are rich in mitochondria(Medar *et al.*, 2020; Castillo *et al.*, 2015 and Papadopoulos and Miller, 2012).

Given that mitochondria serve as a crucial signaling hub, the unique characteristics of steroidogenic mitochondria likely influence various aspects of steroidogenesis in a cell type-specific manner, as the physiological demand for each steroid hormone varies significantly. This variation in hormone levels may account for the differences in the structure, number and distribution of mitochondria across different steroidogenic cells(Bassi *et al.*, 2021).

- **Pregnancy and Prenatal Mortality**
 - ❖ **Cathepsin (CTL)**

Cathepsins (CTSs) are lysosomal proteases that play a crucial role in intra- and extracellular protein degradation for amino acid recruitment and participate in various biological processes, such as the bulk degradation of proteins within lysosomes. In humans, several cathepsins have been identified and are classified into three distinct groups based on the amino acid present in their active site: serine (A and G), aspartic (D and E), and cysteine (B, F, H, K, L, O, S, V, X and W) cathepsins (Turk *et al.*, 2001). Among these, the aspartic CTSD and certain cysteine cathepsins, including CTSB, CTSL, and CTSH, are ubiquitous and among the most abundant lysosomal proteases. (Rossi *et al.*, 2004).

The relationship between pregnancy and cathepsins (CTSs) suggests that various proteases play a crucial role in regulating specific events of trophoblast invasion during implantation and placentation in many species. In rodents, endometrial CTSB and CTSL are involved in controlling normal uterine development during these stages. CTSL's proteolytic activity has been observed in the uteri of cats, pigs, and mice. An increase in CTS gene expression, as well as the localization and activation of CTSL in the pregnant ovine uterus between days 14–18, is regulated by interferon tau (IFNT) (Song *et al.*, 2005). However, earlier data on pregnancy-dependent expression patterns of CTSs mRNA in peripheral blood leukocytes (PBLs) are lacking, despite previous reports of their presence in unspecified ovary mRNA samples (Soderstrom *et al.*, 1999).

Previous *In-vitro* studies have shown that lysosomal proteases can be activated by cytokines, such as type 1 interferon (IFN), specifically IFNB, in cultured mouse macrophages. Type 1 IFN-stimulated pathways are likely involved in various cell types, including blood leukocytes, since these pathways are present in many somatic cells. Lysosomes, which house a significant number

of proteases—most notably cathepsins (CTSs)—function optimally in an acidic environment. The activation of lysosomes is closely linked to the activation of cathepsins in immune cells (Creasy and McCoy, 2011). However, in cattle, the lysosomal activity during early pregnancy, including the gene expression patterns of lysosomal membranes and lysosomal proteases (CTSB and CTSK) and the presence of CTSB proteins in blood leukocytes remain unknown (Talukder *et al.*, 2018).

❖ Inter-Alpha-Trypsin Inhibitor Heavy Chain 4 (ITIH4)

ITIH4, a protein associated with inflammation and tissue stability, plays a significant role in implantation and placentation, thereby influencing pregnancy outcomes. Inter- α -trypsin inhibitor heavy chain 4 (ITIH4), an acute phase protein, has been previously isolated and characterized in the porcine endometrium. ITIH4 belongs to a family of protease inhibitors that includes three other heavy chains (ITIH1–3) and a light chain known as bikunin. These proteins contribute to the stabilization of the extracellular matrix by linking together various family members. The presence of ITIH4 and bikunin in the porcine endometrium suggests their involvement in maintaining the uterine apical glycocalyx, which is essential for trophoblastic attachment during pregnancy in pigs (Ashworth *et al.*, 2010).

❖ Leukemia Inhibitory Factor (LIF)

Leukemia inhibitory factor (LIF) is a critical cytokine involved in embryo implantation and early embryonic development. It is produced by the maternal endometrium during the implantation window and plays a key role in preparing the endometrial lining for embryo attachment (Lessey, 2002). LIF promotes the differentiation of trophoblast cells, which are essential for establishing the placenta and supports the survival and proliferation of these cells. It activates several signaling pathways, including JAK/STAT, MAPK and PI3K, which are crucial for these processes. Additionally, LIF has immunomodulatory effects, helping the maternal immune system tolerate the embryo.

Fig.7:LIF increases the expression of EGF and implantation genes in receptive endometrium. LIF produced by endometrium and blastocyst regulates growth and development of the embryo. Meanwhile, LIF stimulates stromal decidualization by increasing the production of cytokines and prostaglandin. LIF is also involved in enhancing embryo-endometrial interaction through pinopodes and adhesion molecules. LIF stimulates trophoblast cells differentiation and increases trophoblast capability to invade the uterine stroma. Finally, LIF is involved in recruitment of specific cohort of leucocytes which participates in inflammatory response during implantation. LIF: leukemia inhibitory factor, HB-EGF: heparin binding-epidermal growth factor, Ereg: epiregulin, Ar: amphiregulin, E2: estrogen, P4: progesterone, IL: interleukins, PGs: prostaglandins, COX: cyclooxygenase, NK: natural killer, PPAR: peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor, PGE2: prostaglandins E2, hCG: human chorionic gonadotrophin, MUC: mucin, JAM: junctional adhesion molecule (Salleh and Giribabu, 2014).

Abnormal LIF levels or signaling can lead to implantation failure, making it a potential target for fertility treatments. LIF is a key cytokine that promotes the differentiation of trophoblast cells and supports early embryonic development. It activates STAT signaling pathways, which are crucial for modulating trophoblast functions during implantation. LIF is predominantly produced by the maternal endometrium at the time of implantation, with its receptors present on both the endometrium and trophoblasts. By activating STAT3 and influencing integrin expression, LIF facilitates blastocyst attachment. Following attachment, trophoblasts proliferate and differentiate into invasive extravillous trophoblasts (EVTs) and non-invasive syncytiotrophoblasts (STBs). In vitro studies have shown that LIF regulates these processes through the activation of STAT- and MAPK-dependent signaling pathways (Suman *et al.*, 2013)

❖ Serpin Family A Member 14 (SERPINA14) / Uterine Milk Protein (UTMP)

SERPINA14, also known as UTMP, is a protein involved in regulating immune responses during pregnancy, playing a crucial role in maintaining pregnancy and supporting fetal development (Kandasamy *et al.*, 2010). These uterine serpins, currently classified as SERPINA14, which are hormone-induced proteins and secreted in significant amounts by the endometrial epithelium during pregnancy. While SERPINA14 belongs to the serine proteinase inhibitor (serpin) superfamily, it lacks the typical inhibitory function against serine proteinases, suggesting that it has evolved a different role from the usual anti-proteinase activity found in other serpins (Padua, 2009). This gene is found in a specific group of mammals within the Laurasiatheria superorder, which includes ruminants, horses, pigs, dolphins and certain carnivores, but is absent in primates, rodents, lagomorphs and marsupials. It likely evolved through gene duplication after the divergence of Laurasiatheria, indicating its significant role in pregnancy, which may differ across species (Padua *et al.*, 2010).

In sheep, SERPINA14 is thought to have an immunoregulatory function, helping to prevent the maternal immune system from rejecting the fetal allograft by inhibiting lymphocyte proliferation and natural killer cell activity. In pigs, SERPINA14 is associated with iron transport to the fetus by binding to and stabilizing uteroferrin, an iron-binding protein. The function of SERPINA14

may have diversified since its initial emergence in the common ancestor of species that possess this gene (Padua and Hansen, 2010).

❖ Osteopontin (OPN)

Osteopontin (OPN), also known as Secreted Phosphoprotein 1 (SPP1), is a glycoprotein that plays a significant role in cell adhesion and signaling, which are crucial for implantation, placentation and immune regulation during pregnancy. OPN is a secreted extracellular matrix (ECM) protein that interacts with various cell surface integrins, facilitating cell-cell and cell-ECM adhesion and communication. It is widely accepted that OPN engages with integrin receptors expressed on the apical surface of the uterine luminal epithelium (LE) and the conceptus trophoctoderm, helping to attach the conceptus to the uterus during implantation (White *et al.*, 2006).

Research involving pigs and sheep has greatly contributed to our understanding of OPN's role in implantation, particularly due to the extended peri-implantation period in these animals, where elongating conceptuses remain free within the uterine lumen, necessitating significant paracrine signaling between the conceptus and the endometrium (Johnson *et al.*, 2003). This period is followed by a gradual attachment of the trophoctoderm to the uterine LE, which is essential for the formation of a true epitheliochorial placenta in pigs and a synepitheliochorial placenta in sheep (Frank, 2015).

In pigs, the conceptus secretes estrogens during implantation, which trigger the synthesis and secretion of OPN by the adjacent uterine LE. OPN then binds to $\alpha v \beta 6$ integrin receptors on the trophoctoderm and $\alpha v \beta 3$ integrin receptors on the uterine LE, facilitating the attachment of the conceptus to the uterine LE. In sheep, the conceptus secretes interferon tau, which extends the lifespan of the corpus luteum (CL). The progesterone released by the CL subsequently induces the synthesis and secretion of OPN from the endometrial glandular epithelium (GE) into the uterine lumen, where OPN binds to integrins expressed on the trophoctoderm ($\alpha v \beta 3$) and uterine LE (the specific integrins are yet to be identified) to secure the conceptus to the uterus for implantation (Frank, 2015).

In vitro studies have shown that OPN binding to the $\alpha v \beta 3$ integrin receptor on ovine trophoctoderm cells initiates focal adhesion assembly, which is a crucial step for adhesion and migration of the trophoctoderm. This process involves the activation of P70S6K through crosstalk between the FRAP1/MTOR and MAPK pathways, as well as the activation of MTOR, PI3K, MAPK3/MAPK1 (Erk1/2), and MAPK14 (p38) signaling pathways to promote trophoctoderm cell migration (Johnson *et al.*, 2014). Focal adhesion assembly and myosin II motor activity are also induced, enabling trophoctoderm cell migration. Additionally, large focal adhesions form at the uterine-placental interface in both pigs and sheep, indicating the presence of significant mechanical forces during specific periods of trophoblast migration, attachment, and placentation in these species (Johnson *et al.*, 2014).

- Parturition
- ❖ Prostaglandin E2 (PGE2)

The success of labor induction is closely linked to the extent of cervical ripening, a complex process involving significant remodeling and dynamic physiological and anatomical changes, governed by hormones, inflammatory responses, vasodilation and other biological processes (Word *et al.*, 2007). Among the key players in cervical ripening are prostaglandins, which are produced locally in the cervix and uterus, as well as by the fetal membranes. These eicosanoids, derived from arachidonic acid, play crucial roles not only in cervical ripening but also in uterine contractility and the induction of labor. Prostaglandins are eicosanoids, composed of 20-carbon unsaturated fatty acid, arachidonic acid, which is liberated from membrane phospholipids via phospholipase A2. Initially arachidonic acid is converted to prostaglandin H2 (PGH2) via the sequential reactions of prostaglandin G/H synthases-1 or -2 (PGHS-1 or PGHS-2), also known as 1 Fellow, cyclooxygenase-1 and -2 (COX-1 and COX-2) (Terzidou, 2007). Subsequently, specific isomerases and synthases convert labile PGH2 to active prostanoids, including prostaglandin E2 (PGE2; via prostaglandin E synthase), prostaglandin F2 (PGF2; via PGF synthase) and prostacyclin (via prostaglandin I synthase). COX-2 couples preferentially with prostaglandin I synthase and the microsomal prostaglandin E synthase isozymes (PGES 1 and 2) (Smyth *et al.*, 2009).

The five main types of prostaglandins are PGE2, prostaglandin F2 α (PGF2 α), prostaglandin D2, prostaglandin I2 and thromboxane A2. Among these, PGE2 and PGF2 α are the most crucial for cervical ripening and parturition. PGE2 exerts its effects through the prostaglandin E (EP) family of receptors, while PGF2 α primarily influences through the prostaglandin FP receptors (Cowan and Calder, 2004). Multiple sources of PGE2 and PGF2 α have been identified within the reproductive system, including the cervix, uterus, placenta and fetal membranes. Prostaglandin receptors are localized in various tissues such as the myometrium, cervix, trophoblast, decidua and fetal membranes. (Unlugedik *et al.*, 2010). The roles of PGE2 and PGF2 α in parturition have been extensively studied. Research on the impact of prostaglandins on labor and delivery dates back to the 1930s, when it was discovered that human semen induced uterine contractions. This led to the term "prostaglandin" being coined to describe the active substance in the extracts. Further research revealed that during labor, elevated prostaglandin levels act on the myometrium to enhance its contractility, thereby promoting the onset and progression of labor (Tattersall *et al.*, 2008).

PGE2 levels rise significantly in the amniotic fluid and fetal membranes during labor and in term pregnancies, with notably higher levels observed in term births compared to preterm births. As labor progresses, PGF2 α levels also increase, and both PGE2 and PGF2 α contribute to myometrial contractions. However, PGE2 plays a unique role in promoting cervical ripening and the rupture of fetal membranes. It regulates the synthesis of hydrophilic glycosaminoglycans and enhances elastin activity, both of which facilitate cervical ripening by separating and dispersing collagen bundles (Blesson and Sahlin, 2014).

Applying PGE2 to the human cervix has been shown to elevate collagenase activity in cervical biopsies. Additionally, PGE2 influences the inflammatory response that is crucial for cervical

ripening and remodeling. This response involves the influx of inflammatory cells, an increase in inflammatory mediators like interleukin-8 (IL-8), tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) and IL-1 β , as well as an upsurge in matrix metalloproteinase (MMP) activity (Li *et al.*, 2010).

- **Cyclooxygenase-2 (COX2)**

Cyclooxygenase 1 and 2 (COX-1 and COX-2) mRNA levels were analyzed using ribonuclease protection assays in total RNA extracted from various tissues of pregnant cows, including intercaruncular and caruncular endometrium, myometrium, cotyledons, and cervical mucosa. COX-2, an enzyme critical for prostaglandin biosynthesis, plays a key role in the production of PGE₂ and the regulation of labor. Two isoforms of the cyclooxygenase enzyme, also known as prostaglandin endoperoxide H synthase, have been identified: COX-1 and COX-2 (Smith and DeWitt, 1995).

The two isoforms generate the same prostanoids but are encoded by different genes, which are mapped on different chromosomes and are differently regulated. They provide insights into the regulation of ovarian function, folliculogenesis, oogenesis, ovulation, puberty, the estrous cycle, pregnancy, prenatal mortality, parturition and the postpartum period. Continued research on these markers will enhance our ability to diagnose, treat and manage fertility-related issues.

The integration of molecular markers with other reproductive biotechnologies can lead to faster genetic improvements and the dissemination of superior germplasm. This approach can significantly enhance reproductive traits in both male and female animals, thereby improving overall productivity and efficiency in animal production systems.

Fig.7: The prostaglandin pathway. The prostaglandin precursor, arachidonic acid, is released from phospholipid membrane stores by the action of phospholipases. Free arachidonic acid is then converted to the prostaglandin intermediates PGG₂ and PGH₂ by the action of COX-1, COX-2 or both. Then, PGH₂ is converted rapidly to the PGs by the action of specific PG synthases. Biologic actions of PGs are mediated by interaction with their specific receptors, of which numerous alternative splice variants may be involved. The PGs are rendered biologically inactive by the action of 15-prostaglandin dehydrogenase (15-PGDH) (Slater *et al.*, 2002).

- **Conclusion**

Molecular markers are integral to understanding the complexities of female fertility.

The strategic use of molecular markers in animal breeding not only facilitates the identification and selection of superior genetic traits but also supports the sustainable development of livestock industries. As our understanding and technologies continue to advance, the role of molecular markers in genetic improvement will become increasingly vital, promising a future of enhanced productivity and genetic health in domestic livestock species.

Molecular markers such as FSHR, IGF-1, CART, GDF-9, BMP-15, Zar1 etc. play crucial roles in regulating ovarian function, folliculogenesis, oogenesis and early embryogenesis, which are essential for maintaining female fertility. Understanding and leveraging these markers can significantly enhance reproductive efficiency and genetic improvement in livestock.

- **Scope and Future Prospective**

- Fertility, which has low heritability, requires advanced strategies beyond traditional selection methods for improvement.
- Utilizing molecular markers can accelerate genetic improvement in domestic livestock species, including buffalo.
- Combining molecular markers with other reproductive biotechnological tools can lead to faster genetic advancements and the spread of superior genetic material.

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